

Supplementary File 5. Information on the excluded studies

No.	Author	Journal	Title	Reason for exclusion
1	Yonsei University	NCT01221558	Effects of Lycopene on Oxidative Stress and Markers of Endothelial Function Healthy Men	Clinical trial protocol of a included report
2	Crowe-White KM., et al.	Curr Dev Nutr., 4(7), nzaa102 (2020)	Variation of Serum Lycopene in Response to 100% Watermelon Juice: An Exploratory Analysis of Genetic Variants in a Randomized Controlled Crossover Study	PICOS did not meet the eligibility criteria
3	Pereira T., et al.	Journal of Hypertension, 33, e151 (2015)	Effects of a lycopene-rich diet over the endothelial function and central arterial hemodynamics in young healthy adults	Proceeding
4	Samaras A., et al.	Food Chem Toxicol., 69, 231-6 (2014)	Effect of a special carbohydrate-protein bar and tomato juice supplementation on oxidative stress markers and vascular endothelial dynamics in ultra-marathon runners.	PICOS did not meet the eligibility criteria
5	Tsujino S., et al.	Nutrients,16(19), 3342 (2024)	Age-Related Effects of Olive Oil Polyphenol Ingestion on Oxidation of Low-Density Lipoprotein in Healthy Japanese Men: A Randomized Controlled Double-Blind Crossover Trial	PICOS did not meet the eligibility criteria
6	Cheng HM., et al.	Proceedings of the Nutrition Society, 77 (OCE4), E210 (2018)	The effect of consuming red and yellow cherry tomatoes on endothelial function in free-living normotensive males: a randomised cross-over trial	Proceeding
7	Cheng HM., et al.	Proceedings of the Nutrition Society, 78 (OCE2), E50 (2019)	The effect of consuming red and orange cherry tomatoes on blood-borne circulating biomarkers in free-living normotensive males: a randomised cross-over trial	Proceeding
8	Burton-Freeman B., et al.	Nutrition and Aging, 3, 193–201 (2015)	Processed tomato products and risk factors for cardiovascular disease	PICOS did not meet the eligibility criteria
9	Vincellette CM., et al.	J Nutr., 151(11), 3450-3458 (2021)	Supplemental Watermelon Juice Attenuates Acute Hyperglycemia-Induced Macro-and Microvascular Dysfunction in Healthy Adults	PICOS did not meet the eligibility criteria
10	Volino-Souza M., et al.	Eur J Clin Nutr., 77(1), 71-74 (2023)	Effect of microencapsulated watermelon (Citrullus Lanatus) rind on flow-mediated dilation and tissue oxygen saturation of young adults.	PICOS did not meet the eligibility criteria
11	Dalbeni A., et al.	Nutrients, 10(9), 1310 (2018)	Positive Effects of Tomato Paste on Vascular Function After a Fat Meal in Male Healthy Subjects.	PICOS did not meet the eligibility criteria
12	Ellis AC., et al.	J Nutr Gerontol Geriatr., 35(4), 219-242 (2016)	Modulating Oxidative Stress and Inflammation in Elders: The MOXIE Study.	Clinical trial protocol of a included report